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AN ATTITUDE OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS TOWARDS ERADICATION OF SUPERSTITIONS

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1 INTRODUCTION:

The present era of 21st century is of Science and technology. Science demands the proof for any belief or opinion and one must prove his/her statement on experimental basis. Human race is being developing his day to day life with the help of science and technology. Till also there are many superstitions or misbeliefs have occurred in human being which as step forwarded from generation to generation.

India is the leading country in the Science and Technology. Till date the people of the India are most superstitious and lack Scientific Attitude. The Education plays an important role in the development of country. Teacher plays vital role in developing his students which are future citizens of India. As Indian Society is suffered from various superstitions, teachers and students may also have some sort or little bit high superstitions.

The superstitious beliefs are those which have been demonstrated to be at variance with the objective facts, are likely to be shared by many members of a society (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975)⁴. According to the study Santhi (1982), superstitious beliefs are prevalent among people belonging to all strata of society and among people of all levels of formal education. In another study prevalence of superstitious beliefs were found among first year college female students, while intelligence, creativity and academic ability were found inversely related to the superstitious beliefs⁵.

A superstition is an irrational belief arising from ignorance. Superstitions are based on the beliefs that future events are influenced by specific behaviors, without having a causal relationship. Most of superstitions involve ensuring good luck or making good things happen. There are so many activities of our daily life which are affected by inherited superstitions⁶.

The advancement of awareness and intellectual integrity is promoted by all Educational Institutions and yet many College Students routinely put themselves in the hands of fate. According to the study, the odds an undergraduate was wear lucky clothing as part of a behavioral, ritual or superstitions are 1 in 3.26 and the odds that they was strive to avoid 'jinxes' are almost double i.e. 60%. Superstitious beliefs and behavior are common among different groups of high school and university. According to another study it was found that superstitiousness was more prevalent among females and arts students than males and science students, according to 1910 study from American Journal of Insanity, "there is infinite rest in believing in something. Even if that something was at some future day prove insufficient."⁷

These sort of superstitions may caused in pre-service teachers due to reasons such as lack of experience, fear of examination, outstation students, obsessive compulsive disorder, study of tradition or culture, role of T.V. superstitions based movies, novels and literature, human tendency, personal anecdotes⁸.

These superstitions affect pre-service teachers' life in the ways such as loss of concentration, lack of interest in studies, hampering the development of an individual personality and one's belief strengthens another's.

To reduce these superstitions, teachers can play a key role and hence there is need to make the teachers aware about such kinds of superstitions at their pre-service training and hence the current study would be useful in some sort.

If the teachers have the awareness about superstitions and its harmful effects, he/she will be able to maintain himself/herself with rational thinking. Also they definitely will try to escape the society from the darkness of superstitious beliefs which is supposed the major obstacle in the progress of the nation. In the consequence to enrich the attitude about pre-service teachers about superstitions, the present study was play important role.

2 NEED AND IMPORTANCE:

2.1 NEED:

1. It has been recognized that many superstitions are still prevalent in all fields of life, education field is also not exception.
2. Superstitions affects the quality of livelihood in all aspects.
3. Superstitious beliefs are harmful to the welfare of society so also for the development of the nation.
4. Superstitiousness affects the personality of an individual which in turn harmful to build up the scientific approach.
5. Many highly educated people also pre-service teachers have been recognized with superstitious beliefs.
6. There is need to create the resource persons to implement the attitude about eradication of superstitions in the society. The teachers was become best resources.
7. The pre-service teachers can be enriched in the attitude about eradication of superstitions during their pre-service training course. There is need to identify the student teachers with low attitude.

2.2 IMPORTANCE OF STUDY :

1. Present study is helpful to find the attitude about eradication superstitions in pre-service teachers.
2. The present study is useful to find out the causes of superstitions in pre-service teachers.
3. The present study is helpful to develop a program to make the pre-service teachers thinking rationally.
4. The teachers are supposed to play an important role in the awareness about eradication of superstitions among the society. Therefore, it is important to create rational thinking in pre-service teachers. The present study is useful in this sense.
5. Superstitions are still prevalent in this modern world. This prevalence may block the well being of the individuals and hinder their positive personal growth. Hence

there is need to eradicate these superstitions from the school level. for this purpose the attitude of teachers about eradication of superstitions is very important and hence the study is important to know the attitude of pre-service teachers about eradication of superstitions.

3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

“To study an attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.”

4 OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

- **Attitude about eradication of superstitions :**

Attitude about the superstitions means that behavior of pre-service teachers which show his positive or negative view about superstitions.

- **Superstitions**

The beliefs which are based on the blind faith in certain activity or object.

- **Pre-service Teachers :**

The students of B.Ed. course studying under University of Pune are said to be pre-serviced teachers.

- **Rural and urban pre-service teachers:**

The pre-service teachers are those pre-service teachers having their parents from rural or urban area.

- **Science pre-service teachers:**

The science pre-service teachers are those pre-service teachers who had completed their graduation from science stream.

- **Non-science pre-service teachers:**

Non-science pre-service teachers are those pre-service teachers who had completed their graduation other than science stream.

5 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To test attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.
2. To compare attitude towards eradication of superstitions between male and female pre-service teachers.

3. To compare attitude towards eradication of superstitions between Rural and Urban pre-service teachers.
4. To compare an attitude toward eradication of superstitions between science and non-science pre-service teachers.

6 ASSUMPTIONS OF THE STUDY :

1. The educated people possess poor attitude about eradication of superstitions.
2. The teachers play vital role to eradicate superstitions.
3. Rural & urban, science and non-science, male and female pre-service teacher holds different attitude about eradication of superstitions.
4. Scientific enquiries/study helps to eradicate superstitions

7 NULL HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- i. There is no significant difference between the attitude of male and female pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the attitude of science and non-science pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.
- iii. There is no significant difference in the attitude of rural and urban pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.

8 SCOPE, LIMITATIONS AND DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY :

• Scope of The Study :

The outcomes of the study are applicable to the all pre-service teachers (B.Ed. students) in Maharashtra State of India.

• Limitations of the Study:

1. The attitude scale used for the data collection was researcher made.
2. The results of the study was depend on the responses of the pre-service teachers given to the tools.

• **Delimitations of the Study :**

1. The present study was delimited to the Pune City of the Maharashtra State in India.
2. The study was delimited to only Education Colleges in Pune City.
3. The research was delimited to only the pre-service teachers.
4. The present study was delimited to attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.

9 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY :

• **Research Method :**

Survey Method was used for this study

• **Population And Sampling:**

i) **Population :**

Population of the present study was included all pre-service teachers in the Education Colleges of Maharashtra state.

ii) **Sample:**

From ten Colleges of Education 40 pre-service teachers from each college means 400 pre-service teachers were selected as a sample.

iii) **Tools For Data Collection:**

The researcher made Attitude Scale about eradication of superstitions was used for the data collection.

iv) **Statistical Techniques for Data Analysis:**

The data was analyzed by using mean, standard deviation and t-test as statistical techniques.

10 ATTITUDE SCALE AND MEAN:

To know the attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions the attitude scale was collected from pre-service teachers, scrutinized, tallies were converted into scores of individual respondent. From these scores frequency distribution was prepared and mean was calculated.

Table 1 Scale for Attitude towards eradication of superstitions

Sr. No.	Range of Scores	Description
1	211-250	Strongly Positive
2	171-210	Positive
3	131-170	Average
4	91-130	Negative
5	Below 90	Strongly Negative

Table 2 mean scores for Attitude towards eradication of superstitions

No. of Respondents(N)	Total scores	Total scores obtained	Sample Mean
400	100000	75168	187.92

Fro table 2 , the range of mean scores of attitude scale shows that the attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions is positive.

11 TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS:

- **The hypothesis no. 1 :**

To test this hypothesis the researchers compared the attitude of male and female pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.

Table 3 Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of male and female pre-service teachers' ASES scores.

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t- cal	df	t table	Sig level	Null hypothesis
Male	75	188.48	20.84	0.29	398	1.97	0.05.	Accepted
Female	325	187.79	18.37					

In case of male and female pre-service teachers, the t-value calculated for group differences was 0.29 which is less than table value i.e. 1.97 and was not significant at 0.05 level. This shows that there is no significant difference in attitude of male and female pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions. In the light of this finding the null hypothesis no. 1 is accepted.

• **Testing of hypothesis no.2. :**

Table 4 Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of Science and non science pre-service teachers' ASES scores.

Subject of graduation	N	Mean	S.D.	t-cal	df	t table	Sig level	Null hypothesis
Science	123	189.91	18.51	1.41	398	1.97	0.05.	Accepted
Non Science	277	187.03	18.94					

In case of Science and non science pre-service teachers, the t-value calculated for group differences was 1.41 which is less than table value i.e. 1.97 and was not significant at 0.05 level. This shows that there is no significant difference in attitude of Science and non science pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions. In the light of this finding the null hypothesis no. 2 is accepted.

From the mean of Science and non science student teachers' scores, it was seen that that the attitude of Science and non science student teachers towards eradication of superstitions was positive.

Testing of hypothesis no.3 :

To test this hypothesis the researcher compared the attitude of rural and urban pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions. From the scores of science and non-science pre-service teachers mean, standard deviation and t-value was calculated.

Table 5 Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of rural and urban pre-service teachers' ASES scores.

Sr. no	Area	N	Mean	S.D.	t-cal	df	t table	Sig level	Null hypothesis
1	Rural	133	189.8271	20.11	1.43	398	1.97	0.05.	Accepted
2.	Urban	267	186.97	18.12					

In case of rural and urban pre-service teachers, the t-value calculated for group differences was 1.43 which is less than table value i.e. 1.97 and was not significant at 0.05 level. This shows that there is no significant difference in attitude of rural and urban pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions . In the light of this finding the null hypothesis no. 3 is accepted.

From the mean of rural and urban student teachers' scores, it was seen that that the attitude of rural and urban student teachers towards eradication of superstitions was positive.

12 CONCLUSIONS:

The conclusions of the study are as follows :

1. The pre-service teachers have positive attitude towards eradication of superstitions which are prevalent in society.
2. Gender did not matter on attitude towards eradication of superstitions among pre-service teachers,
3. The subject of graduation of pre-service teachers has no impact on attitude towards eradication of superstitions.
4. There is no relation of rural or urban background of pre-service teachers with positive or negative attitude towards eradication of superstitions.

13 CONTRIBUTION OF PRESENT RESEARCH TO EDUCATION:

1. Present study gives the idea about attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.
2. On the basis of the results obtained by researcher, the further efforts can be made to increase the attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.
3. The study highlights the need of remedial programs to increase the attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.
4. The role of Teacher-Educator to develop an attitude of pre-service teachers towards eradication of superstitions.

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